

which might exist. Or, in still other instances, an actual organic esophageal stenosis due to tuberculous infiltration of the "party wall" might be present. Nevertheless, Dr. Levy's point was well taken. Dr. Jackson hoped that fulguration and carbon dioxide snow would be thoroughly tried out, but he had had no experience with either. He had not employed the Abderhalden test, as suggested by Dr. Beck, but all diagnostic methods should be used. With reference to the dosage of radium, he said a small dose, such as ten milligrams, acts as an irritant, because it cannot be left long enough in the esophagus. A hundred milligrams left in for an hour or more was usually required. He did not speak as an authority; he depended upon Dr. W. H. Cameron and Dr. William Proescher for dosage and duration of the radium application in each particular case.

Suspension Laryngoscope in Children. DR. ROBERT LEVY, Denver.

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DISCUSSION.

DR. SIDNEY YANKAUER agreed with all Dr. Levy said concerning suspension laryngoscopy. He has performed a number of operations with this apparatus, one of which he reported before the Eastern Section of this Society. After several operations by the general surgeons, the patient's neck was so scarred that the lumen of the larynx was so small that he could hardly get a probe through. The arytenoids were so adherent to the epiglottis that by the ordinary direct methods the lumen could not be seen, but with suspension laryngoscopy this could be accomplished. The passage of the first probe was followed by a larger, and finally he could pass a uterine dilator. By means of the uterine dilator he could stretch the larynx sufficiently to get a rubber tube in, which was left *in situ* for two weeks, when a larger one was used. It was thus possible, finally, to introduce the intubation tube. The boy is now going about, and has been wearing the intubation tube for about four months. The suspension laryngoscope had been modified by Killian himself as well as by others. The new model which Killian has brought out does not appear as useful as the original model. He has not been able to bring the anterior commissure into view with the new device.

DR. SAMUEL IGLAUER was interested in Dr. Levy's remarks, and agreed with practically every point. While it is true that the procedure is less difficult in children, it can be carried out satisfactorily in adults. In bringing the anterior commissure into view, one should use counter-pressure with Albrecht's instrument, or the finger. Killian recommends a dose of codein preliminary to the anesthetic, in children. He has frequently followed this suggestion. Atropin should be used with ether in order to dry up the secretions.

He has tried tonsil removal under suspension, but thinks the Beck method far superior and much simpler than that of Killian. Referring to the removal of a broken safety-pin from the larynx of the child, 5 years of age, he really did not completely suspend the patient. He introduced the spatula and while supporting the spatula (and thus the patient's head) with his left hand, he could see the foreign body and remove it immediately with the forceps in his right hand. He has recently intro-

duced radium into the larynx in the treatment of a papilloma in a young child. In another infant radium was applied to the outside of the larynx. He does not know the dosage because he did not own the radium.

DR. THOMAS J. HARRIS confirmed what Dr. Levy had said with reference to the simplicity of the method in children and the wonderful view of the larynx obtained in the average case. He referred briefly to a case in which he applied radium in a child, 6 years of age, using the suspension apparatus, with rectal anesthesia, one hundred milligrams of radium, of one million activity, being applied for twenty minutes. The first time he attempted to apply the radium, without the suspension apparatus, he thought it went into the esophagus instead of into the larynx. When the apparatus was employed it was very much easier to see the papilloma and to make the application of radium. He recommended the use of rectal anesthesia in these cases.

DR. LEVY, in closing the discussion, said that he had not found the report of Dr. Yankauer's case in his search for all cases to date in which suspension laryngoscopy had been employed in children. He thought the old Killian method of suspension apparatus better in children, but in adults he liked the Albrecht or Howorth modification. He had used cocain in adults, but in children he used general anesthesia. Morphin and hyoscin in cases in which a large percentage of cocain did not seem to abolish the laryngeal reflex were useful in adults. He has never been able to see why adrenalin was added to the cocain, inasmuch as it is not an anesthetic and as there is very little loss of blood in these cases. In some cases of children with chloroform anesthesia, the adductors contracted, the vocal bands came together, and the spasm of the larynx continued for some time. In such cases a dilute solution of cocain was of advantage.

The Clinical Significance of Bacteremia. DR. JOHN E. SHEPPARD, Brooklyn.

Four cases are reported, which seemed to the author to be fairly illustrative of a considerable series of cases encountered at the Jewish Hospital in Brooklyn. The four cases and others of the group from which these were selected, would appear to demonstrate that not all cases of otitic bacteremia need operation. To distinguish between cases which do and those which do not require operation calls for one's closest observation and best judgment.

As aids, all too meager at times it is true, in coming to a conclusion as to whether or not to operate, the author suggests the following points: (1) The general condition and appearance of the patient. Is there a markedly septic condition? Is it increasing or decreasing? As of the greatest aid in determining this, (2) The temperature curve. (3) Whether the process is localizing or tending to become general. (4) Blood counts, frequent enough to keep a careful line on the patient's resisting power. (5) Blood cultures, sufficiently often to have a definite knowledge of the persistence of the organism in the blood, and whether the number of colonies per cubic centimeter is increasing or diminishing, thus showing whether or not the patient is in need of assistance in taking care of the bacteremia.